

Transcriptomic Analysis of the Response of *hiPSC*-derived Cardiac Progenitors to Microgravity

Bernat Frangi^{1,*}, Marcos Martín-Romo¹, Rodrigo Cervera¹, and Luis Grau¹

¹Carlos III University, Higher Polytechnic School, Leganés, 28911, Spain

*bernat.frangi@alumnos.uc3m.es

ABSTRACT

The cellular response to microgravity has been studied extensively, but the effects of space microgravity on human cardiac progenitors are not well understood. To address this gap in knowledge, we conducted a study to evaluate the impact of space microgravity on the mRNA expression of *human induced pluripotent stem cell* (hiPSC)-derived cardiac progenitors. Cardiac progenitors were cultured for 3 weeks on the International Space Station (ISS), and their growth, differentiation and mRNA expression were compared to those of space 1G and ground cultures. Our findings indicate that microgravity cultures showed an increased expression of growth and proliferation markers compared to 1G cultures, improved ATP binding, and increased cytosol and cytoskeleton activity. These results suggest that space microgravity can enhance the growth and proliferation of hiPSC-cardiomyocytes.

Introduction

Cardiomyocytes derived from human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSC-CMs) are a promising source for regenerative cardiac therapy^{1,2}. However, improving the efficiency of hiPSC-CM production remains a challenge. Microgravity, which can modulate cell properties and increase stem cell proliferation^{3,4}, presents a novel method for achieving high-efficiency cardiomyocyte differentiation. While simulated microgravity generated with a random positioning machine has shown promising results⁵, the International Space Station (ISS) provides a unique environment to study the effect of space microgravity on cell properties. Recent developments in cryopreserving 3D cardiac progenitors and culturing them in a CO₂-independent medium have allowed for the study of the effects of space microgravity on the culture and differentiation of 3D cardiac progenitors on the ISS⁶. In this study, cryopreserved hiPSC-derived cardiac progenitors (hiPSC-CPs) were sent to the ISS and were successfully cultured for 3 weeks. Our assessment of the cells showed that space microgravity increased cell growth and proliferation and generated cardiomyocytes with appropriate internal structural and functional features.

Materials and Methods

The methods used in this experiment are divided into two parts:

1. Cell culture and obtention of the genetic data through RNA-seq (**Figure 1**).
2. Data processing, analysis and biological interpretation (**Figure 2**).

Figure 1. Graphical overview of the cell culture and the obtention of the genetic data through RNA-seq.

The first point (cell culture and obtention of the genetic data) has not been repeated, as it was already done in another study published in *Stem Cell Reports* journal⁷. The raw gene data has been taken from such study. Therefore, the work of this paper

Figure 2. Graphical overview of the data processing, analysis and biological interpretation.

begins at the data processing stage. All the steps from Data Filtering to Gene Selection were done using R Studio, and the Functional Annotation was done using the Database for Annotation, Visualisation and Integrated Discovery (DAVID).

Results

Data Filtering and Quality Control

In this part of the experiment, the genes were filtered based on counts per million (CPM) and the quality of the data was tested using several analyses explained in the next sections.

Library Sizes

After removing the genes with a CPM equal to or lower than 0.5, the library sizes shown in **Figure 3** were obtained. The first three bars correspond to the library of samples which were grown in space microgravity, the next three to the ones grown in space 1G conditions, and the last three are the libraries of the cells which were grown on Earth. We can appreciate that all of the libraries have a large enough gene pool from which to perform a proper analysis, even though they are of different sizes. This library size variation is sample specific and does not pose a problem for the statistical analysis after normalisation is performed.

Figure 3. Library sizes after removing genes with a CPM equal to or lower than 0.5.

Multidimensional Scaling

Multidimensional Scaling (MDS) was used to check if the data from libraries in the same gravity condition (we will call the gravity condition the ‘explanatory variable’) had statistical similarities, and whether they differed or not from the libraries in a different gravity conditions. The resulting multidimensional scaling plot is shown in **Figure 4**. Green points represent the samples on Earth, the red points those subjected to 1G in space and the blue to the space microgravity cultures (we will call each of these three possible values of the explanatory variable ‘levels’).

Statistical similarity is shown by closeness between points in the plot. In this case, we see that the points of the same colour cluster together, indicating good statistical similarity between libraries of the same gravity conditions. Even so, one point of every level of the explanatory variable is always further away. This effect is probably caused by random errors or by worse quality of the sample due to differences in the culture conditions, as it seems to be an error that is consistent in three of the sample libraries. Nevertheless, what can be easily appreciated is that there is a distinction between samples cultured in the different conditions, indicating a good quality of our data.

One more thing that can be inferred from the MDS plot is the fact that, despite being 1G cultures, the *space* 1G cultures are clustered closer to the *space* microgravity cultures than to the *earth* 1G cultures. This suggests either that (a) the artificial gravity devices used to generate the 1G environment in space are imperfect in their imitation of the conditions on earth or (b) that the difference in the development of the cell on earth and in space is not simply related to the fact that gravity is different.

MDS Plot

Figure 4. Results of the MDS applied to the raw gene data. Red data points are *Space_1g* samples, light blue data points are *Space_0g* samples, and green data points are *Earth* samples.

Hierarchical Clustering

We estimate the variance of the expression of each gene across the nine samples and build a cluster heatmap to study the hierarchical clustering of the gene data. The result is shown in **Figure 5**. The graph represents with the same colour genes which have a similar trend in expression, which highlights differences between samples.

Figure 5. Cluster heatmap of the top 500 most variable genes. The first, second and fourth columns correspond to the *Space_0g* cultures, the third, fifth and sixth columns correspond to the *Space_1g* cultures and the last three columns correspond to the *Earth* cultures.

What stands out in this case is that the *s005_1g* sample, which is from the 1G cultures, is clustered with (is more statistically similar to) the cultures in microgravity (*s001_0g* & *s003_0g*). In fact, this is in agreement with what we appreciated in the MDS plot, as the *s005_1g* sample is the one which is shown closer to the microgravity cultures in **Figure 4**.

As mentioned before, the reasons for this anomaly could be related to random errors or imperfections in the conditioning of the sample. Even so, the hierarchical difference between the space and the earth samples is clear at least, which reinforces the findings from the multidimensional scaling analysis and confirms data quality.

Normalisation

Normalisation is performed on the data. **Figure 6** represents the counts per million as box diagrams before (left) and after (right) normalisation. Even if the unnormalised data looks quite uniform (indicating good quality data), it is still important to normalise to have a common frame of reference from which to compare all of the data.

Figure 6. Logarithm of the CPM before (left) and after (right) normalisation.

Analysis of Differential Expression

After normalisation, the data is fitted using the linear means model without an intercept term⁸. A contrast matrix is used to compute the contrast *Space_0g - Earth* and find the difference in average gene expression between the microgravity cultures and the earth cultures. Genes are then sorted and annotated using the `org.Hs.eg.db` package from Marc Carlson⁹. The annotated gene data is then exported to a `.csv` file called `microgravity.csv`¹⁰. This data is then studied using the tools explained in the following sections.

Volcano Plot

The volcano plot results are shown in **Figure 7**. A volcano plot like this one allows us to know which genes are down-regulated (those in blue) and up-regulated (those in red), as well as the level of confidence in the particular result (given by the parameter B). The higher B, the higher the confidence (the lower the p-value). Gray points have a p-value larger than 0.05, which is the threshold considered in this plot for statistical reliability in the results. In future parts of the analysis, we use different threshold values to remove or discard the less reliable results of the statistical test.

From this plot, we can easily pick out some of the most up-regulated or down-regulated genes with the highest B values. For example, the topmost blue point corresponds to the transcript ENSG00000068976, which can be found to be the PYGM gene (glycogen phosphorylase) from the annotation performed in previous sections. This muscle associated gene is down-regulated in the space cultures. Other down-regulated genes include HSPA5 (heat shock protein family A member

Figure 7. Volcano plot of the differential gene expression. Blue points correspond to down-regulated genes and red points correspond to up-regulated genes. Gray points are genes with a p-value larger than 0.05, which is the threshold considered in this plot for statistical confidence in its results.

5), ZNF280B (zinc finger protein 280B) and GJA5 (gap junction protein alpha 5)⁹. Some up-regulated genes include SLC44A2 (solute carrier family 44 member 2), RBM3 (RNA binding motif protein 3) and ANKRD1 (ankyrin repeat domain 1)⁹.

Gene selection

The data from `microgravity.csv` contains the differential expression data of all the notably expressed genes in our original data. It contains both under and over-expressed genes. In this step, we use the Python script `filter_genes.py` to obtain two files, `over_expressed.csv` and `under_expressed.csv`¹⁰, with, respectively, the top over- and under-expressed genes in `microgravity.csv`. In order to do this selection, we choose a threshold value for the adjusted p-value. All genes with p-value over the threshold are discarded. In this experiment, we choose a p-value threshold of 0.001.

DAVID Analysis

The lists of up-regulated and down-regulated genes are analysed for main biological components and functions separately using DAVID. The output tables obtained from DAVID can be found [here](#)¹⁰.

In terms of up-regulated genes, the principal biological components present were the cytoplasm and the cytoskeleton. Furthermore, the most enriched clusters in the over-expressed gene list were related to **cytoplasmic activity** (translation of mRNA, ribosomal activity and structure, ribosomal proteins, and RNA binding), **cell-cell adhesion** (adherens junction and cadherin binding) and **ionic activity** (metal binding sites, metallothioneins, cellular response to ions, detoxification of copper ion, mineral absorption and homeostasis).

Gene ontology results for over-expressed genes showed increased expression of ontologies related to the **cytosol** (cytoplasm, ribosomes, focal adhesion, the cytoskeleton, the nucleus, vesicles, and the transmembrane transporter complex), **proliferation** (cytoplasmic translation, cellular response to several ions, cell proliferation regulation, growth regulation, inflammatory response regulation, homeostasis, cell-cell adhesion, pH regulation, mRNA processing, angiogenesis, ubiquitin transferase activity, and, interestingly, hepatocyte differentiation) and **RNA structure** (structural constituents of ribosome, protein binding, RNA binding, amino acid transport activity, actin binding, protein N-terminus binding and ATPase activity).

In terms of down-regulated genes, the main clusters were related to the **extracellular matrix** (structure and organization), **metabolism and biosynthesis of lipids** (cholesterol, sterol, and steroids), **endoplasmic reticulum, proteins** (signalling, glycoproteins and disulphide bond) and **extracellular space** (including secretion).

Gene ontology results for under-expressed genes involved the **extracellular matrix** (structural components, integrin binding), **ion binding** (iron ion, calmodulin, calcium ion), **ion channel activity and regulation** (potassium channels) and **identical/misfolded protein binding**.

Cytoscape Analysis (STRING enrichment)

A filtered list of the first 2000 genes with the lowest p-value from `microgravity.csv` is analysed in Cytoscape (via STRING enrichment) to look for affected biological processes, molecular functions and cellular components. A network of each gene whose logFC determines its color (red are over-expressed and blue are under-expressed) is represented when a desired output is found. The output from Cytoscape can be found [here](#)¹⁰.

One of the over-expressed networks revealed by STRING is **ATP binding**. It shows a slightly higher number of over-expressed genes than under-expressed genes. However, most of the findings revealed under expression of several biological processes and functions, such as the ones shown on **Figure 8**.

Figure 8. Left: Heart development network. Right: Heart morphogenesis network. under-expressed genes are in blue while over-expressed genes are in red.

The network of **focal adhesion** network showed a majority of under-expressed genes, and the network of **cell junction** was slightly under-expressed too. Furthermore, the network related to **regulation of growth** was also under-expressed.

Most surprisingly, the networks related to **heart morphogenesis** and **heart development** were primarily comprised of under-expressed genes.

Discussion

The DAVID tool has furnished valuable insights into our study of cells in a microgravity environment, allowing us to draw several biological interpretations. One notable finding regarding the response of cardiomyocytes to microgravity is that it strongly enhances their growth. Compared to cardiomyocytes on Earth, those in microgravity exhibit higher levels of cytoskeleton and cytosol activity, indicating increased activity in the cell's nuclei and other organelles. Additionally, RNA structure and activity, ribosomal activity, and intracellular transport and connectivity are all over-expressed. These observations are consistent with the findings on proliferation and growth, as all of these processes are crucial for the synthesis of proteins needed for cell growth and proliferation.

In addition, the observation of cell proliferation suggests that the cells are undergoing mitosis and generating new material. This likely leads to a decrease in extracellular space and matrix, which aligns with the findings of the under-expressed gene list analysis performed using DAVID. Another effect of increased cell proliferation is increased cell adhesion, as the larger number of cells in the same space and their larger size will make them become very compacted. This, in turn, can make transport between the cells difficult, resulting in lower ion binding and ion channel activity compared to cells on Earth.

A limitation of using DAVID for functional analysis is that it solely provides information about the functions of the genes entered into the tool, without taking into account gene interactions and regulation. This becomes problematic when analyzing cellular functions that are both over and under-expressed via different genes. For those functions, the overall effect of this differential expression cannot be determined, as we lack knowledge of how these genes interact with each other. As a solution, we can broaden our analysis by performing STRING Enrichment in Cytoscape.

In the case of ion binding and ion transport, DAVID showed both under and over-expressed genes. In the ion binding network from Cytoscape and STRING enrichment, a greater number of under-expressed genes can be observed. This implies that ions are less tightly bound when utilized, requiring a larger quantity of ions to produce the same effect. As a result, there will be a greater need for ion transport to maintain cellular functions.

The growth regulation network exhibits a higher count of blue under-expressed genes, indicating a lack of control over this mechanism. Consequently, cells are more at liberty to grow and proliferate, leading to larger cell sizes. Additionally, in the ATP binding network, there is a slightly higher number of over-expressed genes. This signifies that the binding of this molecule during reactions will be enhanced, resulting in increased efficiency and faster cellular metabolism. This, in turn, enables the cell to proliferate and grow more rapidly, which is in alignment with the conclusions about growth and proliferation that we obtained from the analysis with DAVID.

The results of the STRING analysis indicate that the networks related to heart development and morphogenesis have a significant number of under-expressed genes, implying that, while the heart cells may grow in microgravity, they may not develop into a proper heart shape. This finding is crucial when working with cardiomyocytes in space as it may result in the production of dysfunctional and amorphous cardiac cells. Further research is necessary to determine the extent to which this effect may hinder the cardiomyocytes' ability to perform their function.

Finally, two networks associated with cell adhesion are present: one concerning cell junction and the other focal adhesion. Both networks exhibit a greater number of under-expressed genes, indicating that the cells would grow apart and not adhere to one another. However, this contradicts the results obtained from the DAVID analysis that suggest enhanced cell adhesion. To arrive at a conclusive outcome, further investigation is necessary on this topic also.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the effects of microgravity on cardiomyocytes have been studied and several important findings have emerged. It appears that microgravity results in increased cell growth and proliferation, as well as increased activity in the cytoskeleton, cytosol, nuclei and other organelles. This increased activity also leads to increased RNA activity and protein production. However, the extracellular medium and matrix are reduced, along with ion binding and ion channels activity. Furthermore, it has been observed that microgravity also reduces heart development and morphogenesis, which may lead to the formation of dysfunctional cardiac cells. Areas that require more research include the effect of microgravity on cell-cell adhesion and interactions, as well as the extent to which reduced heart development and morphogenesis affect the cell's ability to perform its function.

References

1. Laflamme, M. A. & Murry, C. E. Regenerating the heart. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **23**, 845–856, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt1117> (2005).

2. Chong, J. J. H. *et al.* Human embryonic-stem-cell-derived cardiomyocytes regenerate non-human primate hearts. *Nature* **510**, 273–277, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13233> (2014).
3. Barzegari, A. & Saei, A. A. An Update to Space Biomedical Research: Tissue Engineering in Microgravity Bioreactors. *Bioimpacts* **2**, 23–32, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5681/bi.2012.003> (2012). <https://bi.tbzmed.ac.ir/PDF/bi-20170122121509>.
4. Becker, J. L. & Souza, G. R. Using space-based investigations to inform cancer research on Earth. *Nat. Rev. Cancer* **13**, 315–327, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrc3507> (2013).
5. Jha, R. *et al.* Simulated Microgravity and 3D Culture Enhance Induction, Viability, Proliferation and Differentiation of Cardiac Progenitors from Human Pluripotent Stem Cells. *Sci. Reports* **6**, 30956, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep30956> (2016).
6. Unsworth, B. R. & Lelkes, P. I. Growing tissues in microgravity. *Nat. Medicine* **4**, 901–907, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nm0898-901> (1998).
7. Rampoldi, A. *et al.* Space microgravity improves proliferation of human iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes. *Stem Cell Reports* **17**, 2272–2285, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stemcr.2022.08.007> (2022).
8. Law, C. W. *et al.* A guide to creating design matrices for gene expression experiments. *F1000Res.* **9**, 1444, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.27893.1> (2020).
9. Carlson, M. org.hs.eg.db: Genome wide annotation for human. *Bioconductor* DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18129/B9.bioc.org.Hs.eg.db> (2019).
10. Frangi, B. Code and Data for Transcriptomic Analysis of the Response of hiPSC-derived Cardiac Progenitors to Microgravity: v1.0.0, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14567482](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14567482) (2024).

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Prof. Carlos León Canseco for providing the basic R code for the raw gene data processing.

Author contributions statement

Bernat Frangi: conceptualization, methodology, raw data processing with R, verification and validation, investigation, visualization, writing. **Marcos Martín-Romo:** data analysis using DAVID, investigation, visualization, writing. **Rodrigo Cervera:** data analysis using Cytoscape, investigation, visualization, writing. **Luis Grau:** data analysis using Cytoscape, investigation, visualization, writing. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

Supplementary Information

The raw data, the code and the output files are available on [GitHub](#) and on [Zenodo](#). The accession number for RNA-seq data reported in this paper is GEO: GSE188793.

Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.